

Prerequisites for Creating Textbooks for Auxiliary Schools: Correctional Psychopedagogy for Children with Intellectual Disabilities

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Abstract: *The history of the use of school textbooks as a special teaching tool dates back more than two centuries. Throughout its existence, the textbook has played a significant role in teaching students. It records the amount of knowledge, skills and abilities to be acquired in the learning process. The textbook is a special didactic object, which is both a carrier of the content of education, forms of recording its various elements and a project of the educational process. It implements the substantive and procedural aspects of learning in their organic unity, because the content of education and the learning process are closely interrelated, without each other impossible. One of the important areas of research in the history of pedagogy is the study of the history of school textbooks, a phenomenon that has come a long way in history, and at the present stage is an important tool for learning. The didactic functions of the school textbook are determined: informational, consolidation and control, systematization, self-education, integrating, coordinating, reference, developmental and educational. It is established that foreign and domestic correctional pedagogy has accumulated some experience in the practical creation of textbooks for the auxiliary school. Most of all in Ukraine it concerns textbooks on native language and reading. It was found that the formation and development of textbooks for children with intellectual disabilities in Ukraine were not the subject of a comprehensive analysis that would overcome the fragmentary historical and pedagogical knowledge to understand the historical experience gained in Ukraine and help identify the most progressive ideas and provide useful material for use by authors of textbooks in modern conditions.*

Keywords: *sensorimotor education, abnormal children, development of defectology, special education, psychophysical development, didactic functions.*

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Introduction

The school textbook as a product of centuries-old history, and at the same time, as a carrier of educational content, is always a reflection of its era - the system of values, ideology, culture, worldview, the prevailing stereotypes of modern society. In addition, the textbooks embody the knowledge, scientific achievements of a particular historical era (Chepurna et al., 2020).

Studying the past textbook is necessary to understand the present and predict the future.

In the modern pedagogical literature there are a number of interpretations of the textbook, starting from the simplest, empirical, reflecting the external features, ending with the most abstract, trying to reflect the inner essence. Most judgments about the essence of the textbook comes down to the fact that on the one hand it is the content of education, and on the other - a means of learning.

According to Zuev (1983), "a modern school textbook is a mass textbook that teaches the subject content of education and defines the activities designed by the school program for compulsory mastering by students, taking into account their age or other characteristics" (p. 58).

Bespalko (1988) believes that a school textbook is a pedagogical system, a massive educational book designed for students to assimilate a known amount of information on a certain branch of scientific knowledge and to manage their educational and cognitive work in the process of mastering the techniques of mental and practical activity.

Thus, the textbook contains educational information in the form of:

- subject, scientific knowledge about the methods of activity that are part of the content of education;
- material that helps to master this knowledge;
- the textbook should be presented in the form of books;
- the textbook is designed to serve the organization of training and help manage the assimilation of educational information.

Through the textbook in combination with other teaching aids the content of education is realized (Bespalko, 1988; Behas et al., 2019; Nerubasska, & Maksymchuk, 2020; Nerubasska, Palshkov, & Maksymchuk, 2020; Melnyk et al., 2019; Sheremet, Leniv, Loboda, & Maksymchuk, 2019; Gerasymova et al., 2019; Onishchuk et al., 2020; Maksymchuk et al., 2018; 2020a; 2020b; Bakhmat et al., 2019).

Lerner, Skatkin, & Shakhmayev (1982), pointing to the understanding of the role of the textbook, gives the following definition: the textbook should serve the organization of the whole learning process.

Zuev determined that "the textbook combines the subject content and types of cognitive activity of students" (1983, p. 36).

Beilinson (1985) pointed out that the textbook is a system consisting of many elements, each of which performs certain functions, carries its own specialized service.

According to Bespalko (1988), the purpose of teaching in the textbook should not only be declared, but also provided with content for its implementation. It is necessary to have a clearly defined goal and didactically developed content. Slastyonin, Isayev, & Shiyanov (2001) defined the role of the textbook as educational literature in which the design of educational content is carried out. The textbook is a special didactic object, which is also a carrier of the content of education, forms of fixing its various elements in the educational process. It implements the substantive and procedural aspects of learning, which are closely related and impossible without each other.

The textbook is a methodological tool, it should be programmed not only for the student's activities, but also for the teacher's activities. It does not only gives material, but also determines the method of working with it.

The textbook provides a scheme of coordination of all teaching aids needed to solve each educational task and the subject as a whole, depending on the specifics of the subject, even the topic.

According to scientists, the textbook integrates and programs the functions of other teaching aids, and its system of functions is basic. That is why it is called the leader of educational literature. Other educational publications are grouped around the textbook, and it coordinates their functional use. Almost all editions specify, supplement and develop what is contained in textbooks.

The concept, role and functions of a school textbook

Among textbooks, the textbook carries the greatest functional load. It is characterized by the greatest completeness of functions, the highest level of their integral implementation, as well as the presence of most special functions.

According to Beilinson (1985), a textbook is a workbook that serves to solve and define educational and upbringing tasks, to achieve the goal of this field of education (p. 13). The author has defined an educational book as such, which belongs to the category of specially created tools designed to

achieve certain results in common conditions of the learning process. Therefore, how this tool fulfills its purpose is crucial in the development of its quality and effectiveness, and therefore, the main in the process of planning, preparation and design of educational publications.

Analyzing the works on the Soviet textbook, one can point to the development of only the most general requirements for the textbook:

1. scientific content;
2. ideological and educational orientation of the content;
3. accessibility of the presentation to the level of teaching of students for which the textbook is intended;
4. availability of illustrations.

The author points out the low quality of textbooks for high school compared to the tasks facing it. At the same time, it identifies the reasons that affect the quality of textbooks. Among them he mentions the extreme weakness of the theoretical development of issues related to textbooks, pointing out that before the revolution there was no theoretical research on the problems of the textbook, because there were no research institutions. Therefore, in the pre-revolutionary pedagogical literature there is no work on the study of the textbook, especially in relation to its methodological part. Also, the creation of a quality textbook has long been influenced by various theories and concepts that denied the existence of the textbook in general, proposing in the first years after the revolution to create a variety of textbook surrogates in the form of comprehensive workbooks, textbooks, books of the project type.

The author sees to some extent the lack of proper textbooks in the fact that research institutes after the resolution of the Central Committee of the CPSU(b) of February 16, 1933 did not begin proper work on textbooks, and the People's Commissariat of Education did not oblige them before. Only in 1946-1947 did separate articles appear concerning the textbook by Khodakov (1959).

On other issues, especially the methodological construction of textbooks, views are quite diverse and opposite. The author emphasizes that not even the concept of "textbook" has been developed and what role it should have played in the learning process.

Analyzing the definition of the textbook, given in the works of Goncharova (2015) and others, the author emphasizes that none of the proposed definitions satisfies him, and asks a rhetorical question: "How to correctly define the concept of the textbook?", emphasizing that not every textbook can be a textbook. It can only be a special kind of textbook, characterized by some special features. Taking this into account, a textbook

is such an educational book containing a systematic presentation of knowledge on a certain subject, intended for compulsory assimilation by students. Also, the textbook should reveal the scope and content of all concepts that make up the content of the school curricula in accordance with the purpose and objectives of education, defining for each concept.

For the twenties of the twentieth century is characterized by the definition of methodological foundations for the creation and design of textbooks in accordance with the requirements of the time. The textbook was to express the class, party position of the author, and the content - to reflect science and culture in their development and to form the worldview of students.

Systematization of learned scientific knowledge is defined as one of the most important functions of a textbook. Assumptions were supposed in the sense of debatable problems and unreasonable conclusions.

Thus, the textbook plays the role of a project as the content of education and the learning process, so it performs certain functions.

Beilinson (1985) in the concept of "function" puts the meaning adopted in sociology: it is the role, purpose, correlation with the purpose, i.e. it is what we expect from this product (in this case - from the book). The starting point in the analysis of the functions of the textbook, according to Lerner, Skatkin, & Shakhmayev (1982), should be social goals and learning conditions. In his opinion, these components form a metasystem for the learning process, so their analysis contributes to the selection of global functions of the textbook by Lerner, Skatkin, & Shakhmayev (1982).

The number of textbook functions is not constant. In some lists they number up to 7, in others - up to 22.

Most often, scientists note the following functions: informational, transformational, systematization, consolidation and control, self-education, integrating, coordinating, developmental and educational (Zuev, 1983; Beilinson, 1985).

In addition to the functions mentioned above by the authors, Kodlyuk (2005) also singles out the function of a reference book and social and cultural education.

The essence of the reference book function is to obtain accurate information, especially where access to it is difficult. If the information is publicly available, the textbook can play the role of "the last information station" (Kodlyuk, 2005, p. 35).

The function of social and cultural education involves the formation of the life position of the student, ensuring his socialization.

Some authors link the functions of the textbook with its structure and components and divide them into two groups. The first, didactic, includes informational, methodological and formative. They contribute to the solution of educational problems, the assimilation of cognitive and moral values by students, the socialization of the individual, first of all, it is a didactic function. Under the didactic function of the school textbook, we understand its purposefully formed properties (qualities) as a carrier of educational content and the main book of teaching, most fully consistent with the purpose of the textbook in the implementation of educational content in developmental and educational learning.

Zuev (1983) draws attention to the fact that in determining the didactic functions of the textbook it is important to take into account the specific historical conditions in which the school called to implement the social order of society, and which dictate the methods and structure of the learning process. According to the author, thanks to the didactic functions of the school textbook the most complete and consistent implementation of pedagogic, educational and developmental learning objectives.

Zuev (1983) based on the fact that a textbook is a teaching tool, which has a certain structured book form, for the improvement of which it is necessary to know not only its broad function in the system of society, but also its specific official purpose in the process of implementation learning objectives, in the description of the functions of the textbook suggests reflecting its internal originality (p. 57).

Given that one of the tasks of the educational process was the transfer of relevant information to students, Zuev (1983) as the leading function of the textbook identifies the information function. Its essence is to fix the content of education and activities that are formed in students in the study of the subject, with the definition of a certain amount of information (Zuev, 1983, p. 59).

Beilinson (1985) in his work gives an answer to the question of why it is necessary to highlight the functions of a textbook, in particular, he pays attention to what the optimal number of functions of a textbook should be and why they need to be allocated. The author notes that the more functions are implemented in the textbook, the thicker the book. Concludes that a different approach to defining the functions of a textbook is needed. He considers function, first of all, as a social category, because "in sociology, function is a role, purpose, correlation with purpose. Correlated in importance, method and degree of participation in achieving the goal".

The functions of textbooks are considered in terms of their use for developmental and educational training, in particular: informational,

transformational, systematizing, organization of intercourse and interdisciplinary links, consolidation and self-control, self-education, organizational-procedural, developmental and educational. "For educational literature as a whole and for each of its publications, the establishment of the relationship and subordination of the function is of paramount importance" by Beilinson (1985, pp. 14–19).

The functions (transformational, systematizing, generalizing, motivational, controlling, methodological) highlighted by Beilinson (1985) can be combined into a separate group. They specify and serve the information.

The transformational function of the school textbook is divided into adaptive (ensuring accessibility) and motivational (awakening of interest, development of cognitive activity). It is related to the processing of knowledge included in the textbook, primarily on the principle of accessibility.

Motivational function stimulates the activity of students to acquire knowledge, skills, forms cognitive interests.

Systematizing and generalizing functions are aimed at ensuring a clear logical sequence of presentation of educational material and its generalization at different stages of learning.

The methodological function is aimed at equipping students with methods of cognition, acquaintance with general and specific types and methods of cognitive and practical activities.

The control and corrective function aims to create a relationship "teacher-student", the formation of students' attitudes to the acquired knowledge, to the surrounding reality, the formation of a system of personality integrity.

Beilinson (1985) attaches great importance to the developmental and educational function of the textbook, but says nothing about the corrective orientation of all functions.

The author argues that the greatest functional load among educational books is the textbook, because it integrates and programs the functions of teaching aids, and the system of functions is basic. He considers functionality to be an important feature of educational literature. In his opinion, functionality determines the composition, place and role of the textbook in the system of educational publications, the very possibility of creating textbooks, their design and structuring. It presents all functions in a certain sequence and interdependence from each other.

Zuev (1983) and Beilinson (1985), considering the textbook as a system with appropriate functions, defined its didactic functions by a

systematic approach that corresponds to the systemic nature of the object of study. Thanks to the functions, the corresponding media are determined - the structural components of the textbook.

Another group includes the functions of the textbook, aiming and organizing the student's activities in the process of independent work: the function of planning, self-education, communicative, integrating, coordinating, developmental and educational. They provide the textbook with the role of a skill tool. The function of planning the student's independent activity is implemented in textbooks in the material that reveals the finished action plan.

The function of self-education serves to form skills and abilities to independently replenish their knowledge and applying them. We are talking about the formation of learning skills (organizational, practical, intellectual). The communicative function of the textbook is manifested in the activities of students - in the process of communication.

Purposeful activity of students under the guidance of the teacher, formation of its various kinds, helping them in the course of activity during mastering of a training material, orientation in it and a support on it in practical activity provides function of fixing and self-control.

The integrative function provides assistance in the selection and assimilation of knowledge acquired by students in the process of various activities from different sources of information.

The coordinating function ensures the use of all teaching aids, the assimilation of additional information that students received from extracurricular media.

Active formation of important features of a harmoniously developed personality, according to Zuev (1983), provides the developmental and educational function of the textbook.

Talyzina (1978) developed a functional-target orientation of the textbook, which is based on the analysis of the goals and content of education, taking into account the process of learning and individual characteristics of students. Highlighting the functions of the teacher in the learning process, the acquisition of knowledge by students, the author considers them in terms of implementation in the school textbook and grouped into 5 groups (Talyzina, 1978):

1. textbook as a carrier of educational content;
2. use of the textbook to obtain information about students;
3. the textbook performs functions related to the formation of motives;

4. introduction of the content of education in the process of education;
5. development and introduction to the textbook of educational tasks.

Eremenko (1985) noted that the textbook is the main book for students, which provides a system of knowledge defined by the curriculum in each subject. According to the author, the content of the textbook should be ideologically sound and educational. Thus, in the textbook first of all the educational function should be realized, and the requirement of giving in the textbook of close connection of the theory with practice assumes realization of cognitive activity (Eremenko, 1985, p. 94).

The second group included organizational functions, the implementation of which ensures proper planning and design of the educational process, management and control of learning outcomes.

Lerner, Skatkin, & Shakhmayev (1982) considered the leading function of guiding the process of mastering the content of education. In his opinion, in modern conditions, the textbook is the main carrier of social experience embodied in the relevant model of learning. It is under the condition of a clear organization of this guide that the textbook is able to really help solve the developmental and educational task of learning (Lerner, Skatkin, & Shakhmayev, 1982).

In the textbooks for the first stage school, which implement the ideas of the developmental education of the system of Zankov (1960), the developmental function is highlighted as the leading. Savchenko (1997) allocates informational, developmental and motivational functions as leading textbooks for junior schoolchildren. Zhuravlev (1989) to the leading function, refers to the function of guiding the cognitive activity of students. Zuev (1983) singles out the developmental and educational function in the leading role, since, according to the scientist, it permeates all other functions of the textbook. We fully share the opinion of the author and also define developmental and educational as the leading function of a textbook for mentally retarded children.

Our study is impressed by the approach to the selection of the leading function of the textbook, which is based on the psychological theory of activity. Therefore, the leading one in the system of didactic functions of the textbook is recognized as motivational, the allocation of which "should strengthen all other functions of the textbook", which, in turn, will strengthen the motivational.

It is probable that the considered functions are closely interconnected, and therefore their division is rather conditional. The

combination of functions of the textbook allows you to create a textbook that activates the learning process of students and aims to correct their psychophysical disorders.

Consideration of the functions of the textbook allows from the most general positions to approach the question of the requirements for the textbook in terms of its construction and correctional orientation, because the functions of the textbook are implemented through its structural components.

The analysis of special literature showed that in general pedagogy the problem of origin and development of the school textbook was the subject of study of many scientists. The question of scientific research of the history of the textbook is even allocated in an independent direction. The question of the history of the school textbook was addressed with different tasks and different research methods by methodologists who summarized the experience of their predecessors and studied textbooks of the 19th-20th centuries from historical and methodological positions on the material of geography textbooks (Baransky, 1954). Historians of science studied the history of the subject and its implementation in school textbooks (Olshki, 1933).

Some historians of language, culture, and ideology considered the textbook as a source for the study of historical phenomena.

Thus, the modern textbook is the result of the activities and searches of many generations of scientists and educators who have made a valuable contribution to its development.

Prerequisites for creating textbooks for auxiliary schools

The development of special school textbooks for children with mental and physical disabilities in the historical period since 1917 in Ukraine has been inextricably linked with the development of the content of education and the trends that have taken place in secondary school.

Improving the education system included changes in all parts of the educational process, including the auxiliary school.

The current situation in Ukraine regarding the development of special school textbooks for children with intellectual disabilities requires detailed analysis.

Studies concerning the content of special education in Ukraine show that the problems of teaching mentally retarded children in these years were not solved in accordance with the issues that were posed by the state. Defectologists had to provide a well-thought-out system of educational work, but due to insufficient development of the theoretical foundations of

education and upbringing of such children, in practice used pre-revolutionary methods and techniques, including textbooks of the Medical and Pedagogical Institute for underdeveloped, retarded and Nervous Children in Kyiv. This didactic material had a corrective focus on the development of sight, hearing, motility and basic concepts of arithmetic, reading, writing.

Different approaches were observed in the development of theoretical problems of education and upbringing of these children. On the one hand, the efforts of researchers aimed at developing issues of regime, sanitary and hygienic living conditions, etc. were intensified, and on the other hand, the development of pedagogical issues began. During this period, experimental material is accumulated, which makes it possible to take steps to develop a classification of abnormal children and provide a corrective effect in learning.

Existing theories at the time, which gave diametrically opposed assessments of the capabilities of mentally retarded children, also hampered the development of new, optimistic approaches to the education of defective children. Both Russian and Ukrainian defectologists such as Vygotsky (1924), Graborov (1923) and others played an important role in the struggle against these theories.

Describing the first steps towards the development of defectology in Ukraine, it is necessary to pay attention to the work of the Odessa Pedagogical Institute to combat child defectiveness, which has been carried out since the beginning of 1919. As a result, general approaches to overcoming child disability in Ukraine and plans and programs of training courses for working with disabled children in special institutions were developed.

In Kharkov, in December 1922, the Central Research Station of the Scientific and Pedagogical Committee of the Main Department of Social Education of the Ukrainian SSR began to perform organizational and practical work. Its activities were carried out by two offices: the Scientific Cabinet for Normal Childhood and the Medical and Pedagogical Cabinet for Defective Childhood. These institutions considered the study of children's textbooks, the development of a comprehensive method of teaching, research examination of the physical and spiritual nature of the child through observation in institutions for defective children.

The development of the theory and practice of teaching and educating mentally retarded children in Ukraine was inextricably linked with the development of oligophrenic pedagogy in the RSFSR. This was expressed both in the constant business contacts of special educators of the

two republics, and in the fact that in all congresses and conferences of educators of the RSFSR representatives of Ukraine also took an active part.

In the formation of special approaches to the content of education in auxiliary schools in the 20's a significant place belongs to Graborov (1923), who first justified the need for a special curriculum for auxiliary schools.

Graborov (1923) based the developed program on the programs of the 1st grade secondary school, including somewhat simplified theoretical material and supplementing it with material from the 2nd grade school curriculum, which had a practical orientation (p. 328). For the first time in the program, correctional teaching methods were used.

Considering that the didactic rules of the auxiliary school did not fundamentally differ from the requirements of the didactics of the mass school, the search for the content of education began in accordance with the tendencies that were determined in this direction in the mass school. In the article "Experience of application of GUS programs in auxiliary school", published in 1924 in the collection "Questions of education of blind, deaf-mute and mentally retarded" edited by Vygotsky (1924) the project of the program of auxiliary school based on complex system of training was presented. This program, according to the authors, was to be formed from a mentally retarded socially useful member of the working team and a conscious citizen. The educational material in this project was to ensure the assimilation of specific, accessible material, vital for a mentally retarded child. The main attention was paid to the practical orientation in the environment, the application of strong work skills and the acquisition of basic literacy.

The explanatory notes to the program emphasized that the teaching of the native language should be based on material that is close and understandable to students, namely, on what the child saw, felt, observed, experienced.

Unlike mass school programs, this program had only elements of complexity. It kept the subject teaching of arithmetic and native language. Due to the need to adhere to the principle of individual approach to the student in the auxiliary school, the teacher was allowed to expand, reduce and move the teaching material. The training material was grouped into sections. The training course for these programs was designed for 5 years.

An important event in the further development of defectology was the Second Congress of Social and Legal Protection of Minors (SCSLPM), which took place in 1924. The Congress not only drew the attention of the People's Commissariat to the need for organizational design of institutions

for abnormal children, but it laid the theoretical and methodological foundations of future Soviet special education.

The next stage in the development of the theoretical foundations of the construction of a school for abnormal children was the program by Graborov (1923). In this program, the author tries to overcome the isolation inherent in the pre-revolutionary auxiliary school. The importance of social education increases in the content of education, the local lore orientation of educational material is realized to a greater extent, the number of hours for manual work classes increases. This, in turn, led to the need to redistribute the hours allocated to the study of general education subjects.

Graborov (1923) introduces elements of complexity, which were expressed in the implementation of interdisciplinary links. Among the list of general subjects proposed by Graborov (1923), the subjects of purely corrective orientation (sensory culture and mental orthopedics also stood out (p. 368).

As you know, later it was these ideas of Graborov (1923) that were criticized by Vygotsky (1924), who believed that special correctional education has a deep meaning and cannot be reduced only to the named subjects, since only the unity of teaching and correctional work will ensure the correct formation of the mental functions of the abnormal child and their necessary restructuring. Vygotsky (1924) emphasized that "correctional work should be completely dissolved in the training and education of mentally retarded children". Thus, Vygotsky (1924) foresaw, taking into account the possibilities of an abnormal child, to create the necessary conditions for its development.

In the archival documents of this period there is no information about the development and publication of programs for the education of mentally retarded children, developed by Ukrainian speech pathologists. Therefore, in our opinion, from 1917 to 1926 auxiliary schools in Ukraine were given the opportunity to use three versions of the program, namely, updated programs developed by Moscow teachers before the October Revolution. These programs were not officially approved and were therefore considered a working option.

The first measures to legalize institutions for abnormal children necessitated the development of official and unified programs for their education. Work began on a draft program of auxiliary schools, which was published in 1927, and in 1928 the official, unified programs for educational institutions of this type in the USSR were developed and published.

The curriculum was drawn up taking into account the following principles: coherence and unity, utilitarianism, plasticity, completeness. It

included special preparatory classes for schooling and provided for a five-year term of study. The program also provided for the provision of mentally retarded children with knowledge, skills and abilities of working and cultural life in the scope of programs of the first degree of secondary school.

All work was aimed at correcting the deficiencies in the psychophysical development of mentally retarded children. In particular, the program paid attention to the upbringing of skills and orientations that a child with normative development learns spontaneously, the development of independence, initiative and overcoming the passivity of mentally retarded children.

The 1927 programs were too utilitarian. In determining the content of educational material, preference was given to the attitude to the independent life of the child.

Training was planned to be conducted mainly in the process of productive activity. The children had to use the accumulated sufficient stock of observations and systematized ideas and on the basis of inferences to reach certain conclusions.

After approval of the "Regulations on the auxiliary school", Golovsotsvos Narkomosviti RSFSR issued an instruction letter "On the norms of distribution of working time in the auxiliary school and auxiliary classes" (On the norms of distribution of working time in auxiliary classes. This document, which was considered as an auxiliary school curriculum, determined the number of hours devoted to the study of the sections that were included in the program of 1927-28. These sections offered the following content:

- a) study of life phenomena with organized participation of children in the surrounding life;
- b) sensorimotor education and physical culture;
- c) work on mastering skills in reading, writing, arithmetic;
- d) handicrafts, art education.

The distribution of hours recommended by this instruction letter formed the basis of the first official curriculum for auxiliary schools, approved in 1929 by the People's Commissariat of Education. The programs were compiled on the basis of SAC (State Academic Council) programs for city schools of the first degree and are designed for a 5-year term of study. The main principle of their construction was complexity, ie the implementation of interdisciplinary links in the study of basic life phenomena (nature, labor, society).

The People's Commissariat of the RSFSR outlined the content of education in auxiliary schools, which provided for the provision of children

with intellectual disabilities most necessary for work and cultural life skills and knowledge and awakening in them a lively interest in the environment, education of basic orientations, cognitive abilities, independence in work, inoculation of labor skills.

When teaching mentally retarded children, it was planned to use a large amount of specific material that can be learned directly by students. Utilitarianism was allowed in the selection of educational material. Preference was given to the material necessary for orientation in the surrounding reality, which would be directly related to the independent working life of the mentally retarded in the future.

Despite the critical attitude to sensorimotor education as an independent system of special classes, in the program of 1927 this system of classes was reflected.

Complex material in the programs was selected in such a way that it was easily grouped around the core - the annual theme. Development of sensory and motor areas, correction of speech defects, development of observation, expanding the range of ideas, instilling basic orientation, household, social skills, education of the emotional sphere were important moments of the first year of study. During all the years of study, the principle of concentricity and repetition was implemented.

Conclusions

The structure of language and mathematics programs was almost indistinguishable from the traditional construction, but provided for the inclusion of life-practical material. This used the opportunity to link educational material in these subjects with the main complex topics.

As so far the auxiliary school did not have special textbooks, these programs recommended that teachers use textbooks of the first grade.

Under the programs of 1927-28, auxiliary schools of Ukraine worked for 5 years, during which there was a further improvement of the structure and content of education for mentally retarded children on the basis of the principle of complexity, using textbooks in mainstream schools, adapting their content to the needs of mentally retarded children.

Thus, the period from 1917 to 1928 is characterized by an active search for ways to restructure the activities of the Ukrainian school, aimed at creating a national education.

In accordance with these transformations, which were introduced in the mass school, new ways of reorganization and auxiliary school were searched for in Ukraine. This period is marked by an active search for the content of education, the restructuring of the school's activities on new

principles, by overcoming those features that were inherent in the pre-revolutionary school. The special school faced the task of creating its own forms of work that would meet the characteristics of its pupils (Vygotsky, 1924, p. 525), because the process of teaching a mentally retarded child in a regular school does not achieve its goal. Only with the right education, with few exceptions, mentally retarded children can be prepared for a modest but independent life.

At that time, there were opposing views on the tasks of the auxiliary school. Vygotsky (1924) and his followers looked at the possibilities of mentally retarded children with exaggerated optimism, pointing out that the boundaries of the special school lie in the circle of social goals and objectives of the general and special school. It is in order that a defective child can achieve the same as a normal one, it is necessary to use completely different means (Vygotsky, 1924, p. 58).

The period from 1917 to 1919, Vygotsky (1924) identifies as a period of construction of a new auxiliary school, a period of theoretical and practical research, culminating in the choice of path for a special school.

Vygotsky (1924) believed that "in the life of our auxiliary school, the new academic year will be a turning point." This was determined by the fact that in 1927 Golovsotsvos published programs for auxiliary schools, built on the basis of the latest edition of the SAC for urban schools of the 1st degree. The greatest achievement Vygotsky (1924) considered the completion of many years of work to bring the general and special schools.

Namely, a special school was built on the basis of the general principles of social education. This principle was enshrined in the programs that involved the auxiliary school in the direction of general pedagogical creativity.

This is the answer to the question of the nature of the auxiliary school; the immediate goal of the auxiliary school coincides with the immediate goal of the regular secondary school of the 1st degree.

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